

Determination of optical constants of thin films in the EUV

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Abstract

The determination of fundamental optical parameters is essential for the development of new optical elements such as mirrors, gratings, or photomasks. Especially in the extreme ultraviolet (EUV) and soft X-ray spectral range, the existing databases for the refractive indices of many materials and compositions are insufficient or are a mixture of experimentally measured and calculated values from atomic scattering factors. Since the physical properties of bulk materials and thin films with thicknesses in the nanometer range are not identical, measurements need to be performed on thin layers. In this study we demonstrate how optical constants of various thin film samples on a bulk substrate can be determined from reflection measurements in the EUV photon energy range from 62 eV to 124 eV. Thin films with a thickness of 20 nm to 50 nm of pure Mo, Ni, Pt, Ru, Ta, Te and different compositions of Ni_xAl_x, PtTe, Pt_xMo, Ru_xTa_x, Ru₃Re, Ru₃W, TaBN, TaTeN were prepared by magnetron sputtering or physical vapor deposition and measured using EUV reflectometry. The determination optical constants of the different materials are discussed and compared to existing tabulated values.

1 Introduction

The complexity of functional nano-structures is constantly increasing in the semiconductor industry, and a key enabler for upcoming technologies beyond the 10 nm semiconductor node is new materials. Specifically, metals such as Pt, Te, Mo, Ru start to play a central role as absorber materials in photo lithography, for capping layers or as a means of thermal or electric contacts [1, 2, 3, 4]. Their alloys are used to tune the material's properties to the desired values and therefore must be studied beforehand, which highlights the need for a precise and reliable determination of the physical constants of those thin film materials.

The precise measurement of optical properties in the EUV-regime around 91.85 eV / 13.5 nm is still a challenge for the development of optical components such as photomasks or mirrors for EUV lithography [5, 6, 7]. Due to the short wavelength in this spectral regime, contamination, oxidation, or surface roughness in the nanometer range will affect the optical response of a sample much stronger than for instance at optical wavelengths. Such effects can be the result of chemical processes or contamination by process-gases during the manufacturing or just a consequence of the grain structure of thin film samples. The most important material property for optical applications is the complex refractive index $\tilde{n} = n + ik = 1 - \delta - i\beta$ which, in the EUV and X-ray regime above 10 eV, is typically given in terms of δ , describing the dispersion, or refractive power, and β , describing the absorption, or extinction, of the incident radiation. Since the real part $n = 1 - \delta$ of refractive index \tilde{n} is generally close to 1 and the imaginary part $k = -\beta$ is relatively large, the design of optical components for EUV

applications is non-trivial [8, 9]. An estimation of the optical properties of compound materials can be retrieved from the well-established representation in the form of atomic scattering factors [10], but it is not to be confused with actual spectral measurements of the optical constants. Here, a typical challenge is that the mass density of the compound materials is not known for the deposited thin films, which impacts the refractive index strongly. The most common way to determine optical constants in the X-ray range is through transmission experiments, which measure the absorption of the radiation directly [11]. Using the Kramers-Kronig relation, the complex refractive index can be determined from a measurement of the absorption. Since the penetration depth in the EUV regime is very low, ultra-thin and freestanding films are required for this type of measurements, which has an impact on the accuracy. Another major problem for transmission mode measurements is that the optical properties extracted from freestanding thin films are not always identical to thin layers within stratified systems as they are used in optical components. Measurements on samples that represent the structure of a real optical component, like thin films on a substrate, are therefore much more promising. Such can be studied by EUV reflectometry where the reflectance is measured as a function of wavelength and angle of incidence [12, 13, 14]. In the X-ray spectral range, reflectometry (XRR) is an established method to determine the thickness of thin films [15, 16, 17] and can also be used to determine the optical constants. EUV reflectometry itself is as easy to realize as a transmission mode experiment, but the interpretation of the results is more complicated.

We present here our results of reflection measurements on thin films of the pure elements Mo, Ni, Pt, Ru, Ta, Te and different compositions of Ni_xAl_x , Pt_xMo , PtTe , Ru_xTa_x , Ru_3Re , Ru_3W , TaBN , TaTeN in the range of 62 eV to 124 eV around the energy of 91.85 eV / 13.5 nm, which is important for EUV lithography [5]. Dispersion and absorption of these materials are determined through model fits that consider the effects of interdiffusion, surface contamination and roughness, using a transfer matrix approach [18, 19, 20]. The procedure itself is similar to spectroscopic ellipsometry in the optical regime using the Müller-matrix approach for data analysis [21, 22, 23].

2 Experimental details

2.1 EUV reflectometry

The experiments were conducted in the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) laboratory at the electron storage ring Berliner Elektronenspeicherring-Gesellschaft für Synchrotronstrahlung (BESSY II) at PTB’s soft X-ray beamline [24, 25] which covers the photon energy range from 50 eV to 1800 eV. The beamline is designed for a beam with small divergence (regularly below 1 mrad) and minimal halo. The experimental geometry inside the reflectometer is illustrated in figure 1(a). A monochromatic X-ray beam with the photon energy $h\nu$ impinges on the sample surface at a variable angle of incidence (aoi) θ_i . The elastically scattered wave propagates along the exit angle θ_f , where the specular reflectance ($\theta_f = \theta_i$) from the sample is measured in s-polarization with a GaAsP photodiode. A lubricant-free goniometer inside the vacuum chamber allows for precise rotation and positioning of the samples, aligning the angle of incidence θ_i with an uncertainty of $\pm 0.01^\circ$ with respect to the incoming beam. An example of an EUV reflectance map, obtained on a Ta sample, is given in figure 1(b). The excellent signal-to-noise ratio allows to resolve the data within more than four orders of magnitude.

2.2 Sample preparation

Ru, Ru_3Ta , RuTa , RuTa_3 , and Ta samples were produced on a silicon wafer substrate using DC magnetron sputtering, which resulted in a polycrystalline thin film with a nominal thickness of 50 nm. The deposition took place under vacuum conditions (10^{-7} mbar) using Argon as process gas. Ru_3Re , Te, PtTe , Ni_3Al , NiAl , Ni_2Al_3 , Pt, PtMo , Pt_2Mo , and Mo samples were produced using physical vapor deposition (PVD). Alloys were produced through co-depositing the constituents from separate targets. The deposition took place under an argon pressure of 5×10^{-3} mbar on a rotating wafer drum with spatially separated material targets, resulting in sequential deposition of monolayers and instantaneous intermixing. The deposited samples were polycrystalline with a nominal thickness of 20 nm for Ni_3Al , NiAl , Ni_2Al_3 , and 30 nm for Pt, PtMo , PtTe , Ru_3Re , Te. The typical resulting surface roughness for the samples was classified to be smaller than 0.1 nm (rms). Diffusion of atoms from the thin film into the substrate lead to an interdiffusion layer of few angstroms thickness at the interface between the

deposited material and the substrate. On the surface of the samples, an oxide layer is formed, on top of which an additional contamination layer consisting mainly of water and carbon is found. Depending on the material, interdiffusion layer and oxide layer built up in varying degree and therefore had different impact on the reflectivity of the samples.

3 Theoretical background

EUV reflectometry yields the reflection coefficient R of a sample as a function of the angle of incidence and the photon energy. In case of a thin film on a substrate, the free parameters are the layer thicknesses h_j , the optical constants of the materials (δ_j, β_j), and roughness parameters of the interfaces σ_j . Fresnel's equations allow to calculate reflectivity and transmission at each interface depending on the optical constants, the angle of incidence, and the polarization. Multiple reflections and subsequent passes through the sample lead to interference that determines the total reflectivity of the sample.

3.1 Matrix method

The optical properties of thin film samples under monochromatic illumination can be calculated using a transfer matrix approach [12, 18, 20]. An electromagnetic, monochromatic plane wave can be described by its amplitude A and the k -vector. Following Vignaud et al. [20], we use a notation of upwards (+) and downwards (-) travelling waves in z -direction:

$$u^\pm(z) = A_j^\pm \exp(\pm ik_{z,j}z), \quad (1)$$

which fully describe the state of the system in every layer j (c.f. figure 1) at the vertical position z . The wave in vacuum, outside the full stack of layers, is given by the following equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u^+(z_{vac.}) \\ u^-(z_{vac.}) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{M} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u^+(z_{substrate}) \\ u^-(z_{substrate}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

which contains the 2×2 transfer matrix \mathbf{M} , defined as a product of reflection ($\mathbf{R}_{j/k}$) and transmission (\mathbf{T}_j) matrices [20]. For a thin film of a specific material (*mat.*) on a substrate, including a contamination layer (*cont.*), an oxide layer (*ox.*), and an interdiffusion layer (*diff.*), this transfer matrix reads:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{R}_{vac./cont.} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{cont.} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{cont./ox.} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{ox.} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{ox./mat.} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{mat.} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{mat./diff.} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{diff.} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{diff./subs.} \quad (3)$$

Further layers can be incorporated by additional transmission and reflection terms. A transmission matrix \mathbf{T} has diagonal form, accounting for absorption and accumulated spectral phase inside the material:

$$\mathbf{T}_j = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(ik_{z,j}h_j) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp(-ik_{z,j}h_j) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

with h_j being the thickness of the respective layer. The reflection matrix is calculated from the Fresnel coefficients of the individual interfaces:

$$\mathbf{R}_{j/k} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{j/j-1} & m_{j/j-1} \\ m_{j/j-1} & p_{j/j-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

with the following coefficients:

$$p_{j/j-1} = \frac{k_{z,j} + k_{z,j-1}}{2k_{z,j}} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(k_{z,j} + k_{z,j-1})^2 \cdot s_{j/j-1}^2\right),$$

$$m_{j/j-1} = \frac{k_{z,j} - k_{z,j-1}}{2k_{z,j}} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(k_{z,j} - k_{z,j-1})^2 \cdot s_{j/j-1}^2\right).$$

Imperfections at the interfaces reduce the specular signal. This effect is included here by the exponential term, introducing the interfacial roughness parameter $s_{j/j-1}$ between material j and $(j-1)$ [19]. The optical constants of the materials themselves are encoded in the z -component of the wave vectors inside the materials via the refractive index \tilde{n}_j of layer j : $k_{z,j} = \tilde{n}_j \cdot k_{z,vac.}$

To this end, the reflection coefficient R is the ratio of the incoming and outgoing intensity in vacuum $R = \frac{I_{out}}{I_{in}}$, calculated from the upwards and downwards traveling plane wave solutions of equation 2. After a sufficient distance, the absorption of a bulk substrate would always cancel out all downwards travelling waves $u^-(z_{substrate})$, so upwards travelling waves within the substrate $u^+(z_{substrate})$ do not exist either. Therefore, the reflectivity calculates from only two entries of M_{ij} :

$$R = \frac{I_{out}}{I_{in}} = \left| \frac{u^+(z_{vac.})}{u^-(z_{vac.})} \right|^2 = \left| \frac{M_{12}}{M_{22}} \right|^2. \quad (6)$$

This relationship can be used to calculate the reflectivity of a layered system as a function of photon energy $h\nu$ and angle of incidence θ with the material properties and layer thicknesses as parameters.

3.2 The optimization problem

A typical EUV reflectance data set consists of around 45 angles of incidence between near normal and close to 90° at every given photon energy. In a stack of four layers on a substrate and assuming that the substrate's optical constants are known, (c.f. figure 1), there are 4×2 optical constants, 5 roughness parameters and 4 thickness parameters, totaling to 17 unknowns. In the chosen model, the roughness parameters are independent of the wavelength, therefore there are 8 unique parameters ($4 \times \delta$ and $4 \times \beta$) at each photon energy, and further 9 parameters ($5 \times s$, $4 \times h$) for the global data set across the entire spectrum. At 80 measured photon energies, this means that 649 parameters must be determined on a basis of 3600 data points. The optimization problem is defined as follows:

$$\min_{p(\dots)} \left[\sum_{\nu, \theta} \frac{|R_{calc.}(\nu, \theta) - R_{meas.}(\nu, \theta)|^2}{\sigma_{\nu, \theta}^2} \right], \quad (7)$$

where the calculated values $R_{calc.}$ follow equation 6 and the parameters are $p = \{\delta_{j,\nu}; \beta_{j,\nu}; s_j; h_j\}$. The values for the measurement uncertainties $\sigma_{\nu, \theta}$ for all angles and energies were determined from the experimental circumstances [24]. Although the optimization problem in formula 7 could be solved directly, it is more efficient to break it down into two smaller optimization problems. For a fixed set of layer thicknesses and interfacial roughnesses $\{h_j; s_j\}$ as 'outer' parameters, the optical constants $\{\delta_{j,\nu}, \beta_{j,\nu}\}$ as 'inner' parameters of the optimization problem can be determined individually for all photon energies using a Levenberg-Marquandt algorithm [26]. Thus, we run a global optimization algorithm [27] to determine the 9 'outer' parameters and minimize the optical constants independently for every measured energy. Starting values for the optimizer are chosen from prior knowledge of the sample fabrication for s and h , while tabulated data is used for the optical constants [10]. On a modern desktop computer, this can be solved within reasonable calculation time, using state-of-the-art optimization toolboxes [28, 27, 26]. An example of reconstructed reflectance data is given in figure 2, underlining that this model is accurately able to describe the experimental data.

4 Results and Discussion

Table 1 summarizes the optical constants of all measured thin film samples at 91.85 eV / 13.5 nm, and figure 3 presents plots of the data over the full measured spectral range. It includes the fitted film thicknesses and material's densities for reference. In the X-ray region, the refractive index of materials scales linear with its density and for high energies far from resonances, the refractive index can be calculated through tabulated atomic scattering factors. We used this to fit the density of our samples by comparing the retrieved optical constants at the highest available photon energy of 124 eV (10 nm) to the Center for X-Ray Optics (CXRO) data base [10]. This works well for ruthenium, tantalum, platinum, molybdenum, and tellurium but in the case of nickel and its alloys we still find discrepancies to the theoretical data at 124 eV. Since the overall shape of CXRO data agrees well with our data sets, which is shown in figure 3, it was used for the approximate determination of the density. We find moderate differences in the density to tabulated data, 15 % at maximum. The retrieved density is smaller than the tabulated one, which is not surprising, since the morphology of nanometer scaled thin films is more porous than bulk material. The only exception to this rule is nickel, where we determine a higher density than for bulk, which can be explained through the differences between the reference data to our own measurements (c.f. figure 3(d)) and the resulting poor density fit.

Even in the case that the main interest lies on the values at a specific photon energy, like 91.85 eV / 13.5 nm, the spectrally resolved measurement and fit are beneficial for the determination of the global sample parameters like layer thicknesses and roughness values. For a single photon energy, the here used approach to model roughness through an interfacial roughness parameter $s_{j/j-1}$ within the Fresnel coefficients [19] does not allow to discriminate the effect of roughness from interdiffusion between layers. This becomes possible only by including a specific interdiffusion layer into the model (c.f. figure 1(1)) and measuring spectrally resolved. A measurement at the target energy only would result in a less accurate determination of the optical constants because the problem could be over-determined.

Of the pure metals studied here, ruthenium has the largest refractive power, while nickel shows the highest absorption. Platinum comes close to ruthenium, but at a much higher absorption. The pure metal films mark the extrema in the two-dimensional space of (δ, β) and all the alloys fall in between, as presented in figure 5. The numbers for alloyed metal films suggest that the optical constants of these films can be understood mostly as a weighted sum of their constituents. We find that this is true for alloys of ruthenium and tantalum, molybdenum, and platinum, and chiefly for nickel and aluminum. Although not surprising, these are the first measurements to demonstrate this correlation on the grounds of actual experiments. An interesting exception from this trend is platinum telluride (PtTe), an alloy of the metal platinum and the metalloid tellurium, whose absorption coefficient is larger than that of pure platinum or pure tellurium. The reason lies in the crystal structure of the materials: Platinum telluride's orthorhombic crystal structure results in a lower partial specific volume of tellurium than in the trigonal crystal structure of tellurium's pure form [29]. The resulting, higher specific partial mass density of tellurium in platinum telluride is the reason for the large absorption coefficient of the material. We also note that the optical constants of Ru₃W and Ru₃Ta are almost identical, which is because the neighboring elements tungsten and tantalum have very similar densities and therefore a very similar effect on the optical constants of the alloy with ruthenium.

When comparing our data at 91.85 eV to the existing literature of direct measurements of the optical constants [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36], we find the differences in values, that are summarized in figure 4 alongside those, calculated from atomic scattering factors [10, 37, 38]. Of those references, the data of Windt et al. on Mo, Pt, Ru, and Ta [30], as well as the data of Rodríguez-de Marcos et al. on Te [36], Hosoya et al. on Ta [35] were obtained from reflection type measurements and are therefore very comparable to ours with respect to methodology and outcome. An exception is the value of Diel et al. on Ni [32], which is far off our value and the one from CXRO [10]. Pauly et al. used reflection electron energy loss spectroscopy on Mo to determine the dielectric constants [31] and determined a value that is also very close to our value. The data set of Soufli et al. on Pt [33], who used transmission type measurements on thin, freestanding films, agrees remarkably well with our data. Differences are smaller than 0.5% over the entire spectral range, including the visible absorption edges $N6$ and $N7$ (not shown).

CXRO data [10] and the data of Chantler et. al [37, 38] are based on atomic scattering factors, so in addition, the density is needed to retrieve the optical constants. For the comparison at 91.85 eV in figure 4, we used the natural densities of those materials and not the fitted density values of table 1. If the density is adjusted to the fitted values of table 1, we find good agreement of the CXRO data with our values for many materials over the studied spectral range, see dashed lines in figure 3. However, figure 4 had shown that the values at 91.85 eV differ if the density is not adjusted. Values of the alloys can only be retrieved from the current data bases if their density is known. In some spectral regions, like 70 eV . . . 75 eV for platinum, the spectral shape of the optical constants contains additional information about absorption edges of the materials, see figure 3(c). When working near absorption edges, special care needs to be taken, because spectral shifts and polarization effects can occur [39].

5 Application in EUV lithography

The currently most relevant application of the here investigated materials at 13.5 nm wavelength is EUV lithography, namely for reflective photomasks and mirrors. Their development drives the miniaturization of semiconductor technology by enhancing the resolution of the lithography process and thereby reducing the feature sizes on future computer chips. Since the performance of current EUV lithography masks is the result of a rigorous understanding of the image formation process, a key element is the precise knowledge of the refractive index of the materials in use [8, 9]. These

photomasks are today been used under a chief-ray-angle-at-object (CRAO) of 6° , which corresponds to an angle of incidence range of $\approx 2^\circ \dots 10^\circ$ [40]. They consist of a highly reflective multilayer substrate of alternating layers of silicon and molybdenum and an absorber layer on top [41, 42, 43]. Compound materials such as TaBN, Ni₃Al [1], RuTa [4], PtMo, or TaTeN [2, 3] are currently at the focus of interest for novel absorber materials. Photomasks create a pattern at the wafer based on different physical principles: if most parts of the incoming radiation are absorbed, it is called a 'binary mask'. When phase shifting and successive destructive interference of the reflected radiation play a major role, it is called a 'phase shifting mask' [8]. Figure 5 presents the data of table 1 as an aerial map to visualize the location of the different materials. In current designs, both effects are being balanced to achieve the best resolution, leading to combinations such as 'binary masks with phase shift' and 'attenuated phase shifting masks'. The areas of interest for such mask materials are marked in the presentation of the optical constants in figure 5 through shaded regions. For a binary mask, a high value of the absorption coefficient β is required, while for a hard phase shifting mask, a high value of the dispersion coefficient δ is required, which roughly divides the range of available materials along the line of $\delta = \beta$. Currently, materials with a high dispersion coefficient δ yield the best performance, which means that their real part n of the refractive index is substantially smaller than one, hence these materials are called low- n [9]. Depending on the precise requirements, different materials or material combinations can be chosen. We find that it is possible to tune the material's properties of a thin film by variation of the alloy's constituents to some extent and position it in between the extreme points, marked by the pure metals. A good example is the system of ruthenium and tantalum, who provide great adjustability of predominantly the dispersion. Platinum and molybdenum on the other hand have very similar dispersion values but greatly different absorption coefficients, which allows alloys of the two to be used as an attenuation-adjustable phase shifting material. Nickel-aluminum alloys lie purely within the region of binary masks, but they do not form a completely straight line. This can be understood from the complex shape of the dispersion and absorption curves in figure 3(b), which show that both materials contribute greatly to the spectral distribution of their alloys. For platinum, tellurium, and platinum telluride, the case is slightly different, because their crystal structures are all different [29], which means that the density does not follow a straight line on the (δ, β) plane. Apart from their optical properties at 13.5 nm, for non-monochromatic applications also the spectral shape is relevant. The full, spectrally resolved data of all materials measured is reported online [44] and in figure 3, whereas the chromatic dispersion $\frac{dn}{d\lambda}$ at 13.5 nm wavelength is given in table 1 as a first order approximation for moderately broadband applications. For the application in EUV lithography masks, other aspects than the optical properties of the materials are equally important for success. Central properties are the ability to deposit and etch the materials, their stability and resistance against oxidation [8].

6 Summary

We presented optical constants of various pure materials, alloys, and compound materials, measured on thin films in the EUV spectral region. Our results help to give a deeper understanding of the optical properties of materials that are relevant for EUV lithography applications, especially alloys like Ru_xTa_x and compound materials like TaTeN. The determination of optical constants was accomplished through a model fit of reflection data over a systematically varying angle of incidence and the photon energy. Using the matrix transfer method to model the reflectance data and modern global optimization schemes, this approach proved to work stable and reliable for a broad set of sample materials. Our results extend the existing literature around the photon energy of 91.85 eV for a variety of materials.

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9 Disclosures

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Table 1: Central results of the global reflectance fits for various thin layers at 13.5 nm / 91.85 eV. The density is a best fit value in comparison with the CXRO data base [10] at the shortest available wavelength of 10 nm. Full, spectrally resolved data sets are published online [44].

Material	<i>film properties</i>		<i>refractive index</i>		<i>chromatic dispersion</i>	
	thickness (nm)	density (g·cm ⁻³)	δ	β	$\frac{d\delta}{d\lambda}$ (nm ⁻¹)	$\frac{d\beta}{d\lambda}$ (nm ⁻¹)
Mo	27.3	9.5	0.0728	0.0066	-0.015	0.002
PtMo	30.0	15.7	0.0922	0.0344	-0.015	0.012
Pt ₂ Mo	29.4	17.5	0.0976	0.0416	-0.014	0.015
Pt	34.3	21.1	0.1082	0.0587	-0.012	0.024
PtTe	23.4	11.5	0.0612	0.0751	0.007	0.016
Te	30.7	6.0	0.0352	0.0741	0.012	0.011
Ni	22.3	(10.0)	0.0500	0.0778	-0.002	0.012
Ni ₃ Al	21.8	(7.1)	0.0225	0.0656	0.002	0.003
NiAl	20.9	(5.8)	0.0110	0.0603	0.005	-0.002
Ni ₂ Al ₃	23.1	(4.5)	0.0058	0.0492	0.006	-0.001
Ru	47.2	11.7	0.1118	0.0154	-0.026	0.010
Ru ₃ Re	36.3	13.7	0.1035	0.0196	-0.025	0.009
Ru ₃ Ta	49.1	13.0	0.0940	0.0203	-0.022	0.008
Ru ₃ W	20.6	13.3	0.0941	0.0201	-0.022	0.008
RuTa	45.5	13.4	0.0747	0.0249	-0.017	0.005
RuTa ₃	46.9	13.4	0.0593	0.0295	-0.012	0.004
Ta	46.2	14.6	0.0463	0.0335	-0.009	0.002
TaBN	58.7	10.9	0.0495	0.0318	-0.009	0.003
TaTeN	37.7	6.8	0.0364	0.0438	0.003	0.006

Figure 1: (a) Sketch of the experimental setup for EUV reflectometry at the soft X-ray beamline of the PTB at the synchrotron radiation facility BESSY II. During a measurement, the angle of incidence θ_i is scanned from grazing to near-normal whilst adjusting the position of the photodiode θ_f to detect the specular reflection. The energy is scanned from 62 eV to 124 eV to cover the relevant EUV parts. The setup is operated under vacuum conditions in a lubricant-free environment. (b) Example of an EUV reflectance map, obtained from a Ta thin film on a silicon wafer substrate. The information on optical constants and the sample parameters such as layer thickness and roughness are encoded in the characteristic intensity modulations of the reflectance map.

Figure 2: (a) Simulated EUV reflectance map of the measurement in figure 1(b) of a Ta film on silicon. The dashed cross sections beside and below the main panel provide direct comparison with the measured data (circles). (b) Fitted optical constants of the Ta film over the measured spectral range.

Figure 3: Spectrally resolved optical constants for different groups of materials (solid lines) and comparison to predictions [10] (dashed lines) with fitted density values (c.f. table 1). Dashed vertical lines indicate 91.85 eV / 13.5 nm. (a) Optical constants of ruthenium, tantalum, and their alloys. (b) Optical constants of nickel and nickel aluminum alloys. (c) Optical constants of platinum, molybdenum, and its alloys. Clearly visible are the absorption lines of platinum $N6$ at 74.5 eV and $N7$ at 71.2 eV. (d) Optical constants of tantalum, tellurium, and various compounds materials.

Figure 4: Comparison of the here presented optical constants at 91.85 eV photon energy / 13.5 nm wavelength (red dots) to data from previous studies. From atomic scattering factors: black triangles [10], green triangles [37, 38], from reflectance measurements: blue rectangles [30]. From various other studies: magenta diamonds, Mo [31], Ni [32], Pt [33], Ru [34], Ta [35], Te [36].

Figure 5: Optical constants for thin metal films and their alloys at 91.85 eV / 13.5 nm, all obtained within this study. Binary alloys are grouped as a guide to the eye. Shaded areas depict regions of interest for different mask type applications.